

Taking action to prevent and mitigate pollution of groundwater bodies

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Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Partners short names

Number	Role	Short name	Legal name	Country
1	COO	LEITAT	ACONDICIONAMIENTO TARRASENSE ASSOCIACION	ES
2	BEN	CETRI	CENTER FOR TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH AND INNOVATION (CETRI) LTD	CY
3	BEN	IMT	INSTITUT MINES-TELECOM	FR
4	BEN	WETSUS	STICHTING WETSUS, EUROPEAN CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE FOR SUSTAINABLE WATER TECHNOLOGY	NL
5	BEN	WINGS	WINGS ICT SOLUTIONS INFORMATION & COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IKE	EL
6	BEN	Deltares	STICHTING DELTARES	NL
7	BEN	UNIROMA1	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA LA SAPIENZA	IT
8	BEN	AQUALIA	FCC AQUALIA SA	ES
8.1	AE	HIDROTEC	HIDROTEC TECNOLOGIA DEL AGUA SL	ES
9	BEN	AYTO ALCÁZARES	AYUNTAMIENTO DE LOS ALCAZARES	ES

List of Abbreviations

DMP	Data Management Plan
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ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
WP	Work Package
TM	Technical Manager

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1 Introduction

The following document explains the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the NINFA project. It contains guidelines that will be used for the development of a Data Management Plan which will include an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy that will be used by the consortium with regards to all the data that will be generated by the project. Moreover, the DMP will cover the following aspects:

- Description of the data to be collected / created.
- Standards / methodologies for data collection and management.
- Ethics and Intellectual Property concerns or restrictions.
- Plans for data sharing and access.
- Strategy for long-term preservation.

The DMP will not be a fixed document, but it will evolve during project implementation. New versions of the DMP will be created whenever important changes to the project occur due to inclusion of new data sets, changes in consortium policies or external factors. The final version of this living document will be delivered in the final month of the project as Deliverable 7.3 Final Data Management Plan (DMP).

2 Data Summary

The purpose of the data collection and generation is to assure that the objectives of the NINFA project will be met. The generation and collection of data is critical to the execution of the project in order to meet objectives and ensure that the output can be shared amongst the consortium. The project is part of the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) of the European Commission which encourages open access and reuse of research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects. To this end, NINFA will be following the policy of *“as open as possible and as closed as necessary”* and scientific research data will be easily discoverable, accessible, assessable, intelligible, interoperable and ultimately useable beyond its original purpose.

The conditions of the ORDP apply to the data and metadata needed to validate results in scientific publications and other curated data as specified in this DMP, other data can be included in the DMP but is on a voluntary basis. It requires that the project will:

- Develop and keep an up-to-date data management plan.
- Data will be deposited in a research data repository.
- Ensure that third parties can freely access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate our data with the only stipulation being that the project is properly referenced.
- Provide related information and identify the tools necessary to use the raw data to validate our research.

2.1 Types & formats of generated data

The project will generate multiple types of data over its lifetime due to the multidisciplinary approach. This data will take the form of text document, spreadsheets, laboratory notebooks, diaries, reports, programming code and similar. Furthermore, the demonstration site will also generate a variety of useful data which will be collected and processed.

2.2 Possible re-use of the data

The project will use the data available within the consortium. A number of different data sets have been identified and analysed by the consortium members, then a measured decision will be made for each data set to ensure that if applicable for reuse, that it will be made FAIR.

2.3 Origin of the used data

Data has two main origins, either it is generated from within the project, or it is external data which has been taken from the scientific and industrial community. The origins of this data must be acknowledged within the management plan for each data set.

2.4 Anticipated size of the data

The size of the data produced during the project should not exceed more than 2GB except in exceptional cases as it will mainly be in the form of text, images and occasionally video.

2.5 Data Utility

The data will be primarily used by the consortium members to achieve the objectives of the project, and then subsequently this data will be used for future or related research activities by consortium members. The secondary use of the data will be for the scientific and industrial community that have interests in this field. Considering the use of the data by external parties, particularly attention will be paid to the sharing of confidential information and the IPR agreements included in the grant agreement. To this end, a standardized NDA has been developed by the consortium to allow sensitive topics to be more freely discussed.

3 FAIR Data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Metadata is structured information describing the characteristics of a resource; for example, the dates associated with a dataset or the title and author of a book. Metadata supports discovery, re-use and long-term preservation of resources. Metadata may vary across scientific fields, but it will typically cover general descriptive and access metadata, data characteristics, and archive terms and access policies.

A metadata record consists of a set of predefined elements that define specific attributes of a resource. Each element can have one or more values; for example, a dataset might have multiple creators. Documenting data enables other researchers to discover the data more easily. Metadata about the nature of your files is also critical to the proper management of digital resources over time.

All the partners will agree on specific issues regarding for example:

- The way that the data will be organised or formatted so that everyone working on it now and in the future knows the origins of the data.
- The way that each file will be named (File Naming Conventions). The use of the following format is proposed for each file/document: "project_reference_filename_version". For example, the file containing the public communications deliverable will be called: "NINFA_D7.3_Public_Communication_Materials_vF".
- Providing adequate metadata within the dataset (e.g. field labels or column headings) in order to be easy to interpret the data. Other examples of information that the data must contain include:
 - Reference period.
 - Project funding information: European Union logo and information about Grant Agreement and the action/program that funds the project.
 - Release policy including dissemination rules and purposes.
 - Information about data collection (source, frequency and adjustments).
 - Keywords (Keywords or phrases describing the subject or content of the data).
 - Geographic coverage of the dataset (if applicable).
 - File formats.
 - Comments.
- • Ways to identify different versions. It is proposed in each data set to include a versioning table, additionally to use the suffix "_v1" in each file/document name relevant to the versioning table. For versioning the rule that will be followed will be the use of a sequentially numbered system: v1, v2, v3, etc and "vF" for the final version. If changes need to be done in the final version then the name of the document will change including the relevant sequential version number, ensuring that the document with the "vF" suffix is indeed the final one.

At a minimum, metadata records should be kept in a fielded form, such as a spreadsheet, CSV file, or tab-delimited file. Auxiliary information necessary to interpret the metadata - such as explanations of codes, abbreviations, or algorithms used - should be included as accompanying documentation. The data sets identified for the NINFA project from each work package are included in this deliverable.

3.2 Making data openly accessible

All the data related to Public Deliverables (see grant agreement table 2.2.b) will be openly available as the default. The data related to IPR protection or to relevant provisions made in the consortium agreement will be eligible to be shared under the defined conditions.

According to the type of data and to its confidentiality level, the data will be made accessible on the project's communication channels or repositories (for raw data). This will be defined during the project once the data is better defined and known.

To ensure the safety of the data, the involved participants will use their available local file servers to periodically create backups of the relevant materials. Additionally, a further level of storage and accessibility will be in the NINFA project website (www.ninfa-project.eu) where public deliverables and files can be easily accessed.

A Microsoft SharePoint site, with a Microsoft Teams frontend will be used, among other things, to track project progress, ensure that the information about the progress of each WP is continuously updated, to exchange documents, to collect financial data, to collaboratively prepare reports, to assist in official and intermediate reporting, to report on meetings, achievements and time schedules, and to discuss new approaches and activities planned. This tool will also have the functions of a project handbook describing the project plan, contact lists, reporting templates and Project guidelines. Each partner will update the Microsoft Teams according to the project progress. All information circulated will be treated as consortium confidential unless stated otherwise. The NINFA SharePoint site will include the following subfolders/architecture:

- General
 - Contractual Documents
 - Grant Agreement
 - Submitted Deliverables
 - Reports
 - Guidance and Templates
 - Interim Reports
 - M1-M6
 - Technical Report
 - Partner Financials
 - Periodic Reports
 - PR1
 - Technical Report
 - Partner Financials
 - Online Section
 - Project meetings
 - Kick Off Meeting
 - M6 Management and Technical Meetings
 - Project Contacts
 - Contacts list
 - Risk Management

- WP1/WP2/WP3/WP4/WP5
 - Working Files and Data
 - Meetings
 - Deliverables
 - Milestones

- WP6
 - Dissemination Materials
 - Templates and Logo
 - Final logo
 - Agenda template
 - Deliverable template
 - Minutes template
 - Powerpoint template
 - Website and Media
 - Photos KOM
 - Ninfa roll up banner
 - Leaflet
 - Letterhead
 - D&C Reporting
 - Meetings
 - Deliverables
 - Milestones
 - Workshops and Events

- WP7
 - Working Files and Data
 - Ninfa emails of partners
 - WP Mailing list by partner
 - Meetings
 - Deliverables
 - Milestones

Each work package has its own dedicated area within the folder structure, which is broadly similar to the WP1 example shown in the above. Each work package leader is responsible for the good structuring of the file area and partners are encouraged to follow best practices.

All of the research data and material will be in place for at least the 2 years after the end of the project prescribed by the European Commission, as well as the foreseeable future following that

according to the agreements reached by the consortium by the end of the project (if any additional is agreed).

The Coordinator of the NINFA project along with the TM will be in charge for data management and all the relevant issues.

3.3 Making data interoperable

The data produced in the project are interoperable because the Consortium activities should be based on and strictly follow the Data Management Plan and the Project Manual. Attention will be paid to make the data and metadata interoperable but at this stage, it is not yet clear which standards and methodologies will be used.

All the curated data produced during the project will be put into widely used formats such as Microsoft Office files, PDF, png/jpg images and mp4 videos. For raw data, this still needs to be defined.

3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

This part is not yet defined as it will largely depend on the results of the project activities. At the middle and end of the project, the partners will have a better idea of what data they produced and how to ensure that it is re-used for further research activities.

4 Allocation of resources

Mireia Escaler (LEITAT) will be responsible for the Data Management of the project. Then, each partner is contributing at technical level to provide information about the type of data produced and how to use and re-use it. Therefore, a good communication between all the partners is necessary.

5 Data security

The data produced during the project is stored on internal servers or institutional data platforms of the project partners. In addition, backups will be made to ensure the preservation of the data. Other data will be accessible through the Microsoft Teams/SharePoint platform for sharing within the consortium.

6 Ethical aspects

Any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing can be discussed in the context of the ethics review. The NINFA partners are to comply with the ethical principles as set out in Article 34 of the Grant Agreement, which, among other, states that all activities must be carried out in compliance with:

- a. ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity — as set out, for instance, in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity — and including, in particular, avoiding fabrication, falsification, plagiarism or other research misconduct) and
- b. applicable international, EU and national law.

7 Confidentiality

All NINFA partners must keep any data, documents or other material confidential during the implementation for the project and for four years after end of the project in accordance with Article 36 of the Grant Agreement. Further detail on confidentiality can be found in Article 36 of the Grant Agreement.

8 Collection and analysis of data sets

8.1 Planning

In the DMP there must be the assessment of whether the investment to store the data balances the return on investment that the reuse of the data can give. If that assessment is positive, the data storage must be managed. If this assessment is positive there must be further assessment to determine whether the data is or can be made FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable). Considerations include the EC requirements, ORDP and indications, but also beneficiary organisation policies and recommendations.

8.2 Identification of RESEARCH DATASETS

The research data sets are first to be identified. The idea is to take a “snapshot” of the research data generation. There is no minimum or maximum number of datasets expected but reasonable consideration must be applied. The blank template for the below tables can be found in appendix 1.

Work Package 1

DATA SET n. 1– <Case studies specifications, requirements and knowledge gathering> – WP 1– Owner(s): IMT and all partners providing data		
1 DATA SUMMARY	Purpose of the Data	The data collected and generated will be used to: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Describe the eight case studies (CS) 2. Create a Knowledge database which will be integrated in the Groundwater Knowledge observatory 3. Determine non-technical (surveys) boosters and barriers to the implementation of NINFA solutions (use of reclaimed water)
	Type and Format of data	Existing data on CS1 to CS8 will be used. This will include analytical data (GW quality/quantity monitoring data, etc) which will be in xls, .csv and/or .txt Additionally data will be generated from surveys performed in CS2, CS3, CS4 and CS6 using questionnaire data whose format could be csv, epidata, .sas, and .spss.
	Reused-Data	Most of the analytical data for CS1 to CS8 are existing data freely available on the internet or provided to the project by companies operating within the case study area (Vitens, Catalan Water Agency and Aqualia).
	Data origin	Observational: The analytical data is mostly data freely available on the internet, scientific publications and provided by Aqualia, Vitens, and Catalan Water Agency from groundwater quality/quantity monitoring campaigns. Derived/Compiled: This is the data that will be obtained from surveys conducted.
	Data size	The dataset will be: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Growing: new data may be added, but the old data is never changed or deleted ▪ Revisable: new data may be added, and old data may be changed or deleted For each case studies the expected size will be between 1 and 5000 MB. For the CS2, CS3, CS4 and CS6 the social engagement could provide more data files > 5000 MB.
	Data Security and Storage	Data will be stored on office computers and will be backed up on hard drives and on the institute network drive and backup system. This data is protected. Data sharing between partners will be done using Teams sharing (Microsoft software).
	Data value (Long Term)	The data could be useful to researchers, companies and stakeholders involved in the field of water management.

DATA SET n. 1– <Case studies specifications, requirements and knowledge gathering> – WP 1– Owner(s): IMT and all partners providing data		
2. FAIR DATA 2.1 FAIR DATA - Making data findable	Discoverability of data (metadata provision)	The data generated/used in WP1 will be discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism. The metadata that will be created will describe the type of data, the origin of the data, any filters or preprocessing that have been applied, as well as information relevant to the production of the data.
	Identifiability of data (refer to standard id mechanisms)	Dataset publications will have DOIs for future findability.
	Naming conventions used	The naming convention used will be that described in section 3.1 of this document which is: "project_reference_filename_version".
	Search keywords approach	N/A
	Clear versioning approach	A versioning table will be included for each data set as well as the use of the suffix "_v1" in each file/document name relevant to the versioning table. For versioning the rule that will be followed will be the use of a sequentially numbered system: v1, v2, v3, etc and "vF" for the final version. If changes need to be done in the final version then the name of the document will change including the relevant sequential version number, ensuring that the document with the "vF" suffix is indeed the final one.
	Standards or procedures for metadata creation applied	The metadata that will be created will describe the type of data, the origin of the data, any filters or preprocessing that have been applied, as well as information relevant to the production of the data.
2.2 FAIR DATA – Making data openly accessible	Data openly available or kept close	Non sensitive data from case studies and surveys will be openly available. Any data judged sensitive by the consortium will remain private for use only in the consortium.
	How data will be made available	The data related to the WP1 will be published open access on a freely accessible repository. It will also be made available in NINFA open repository.
	Methods or SW tools for data access	No specific need
	SW documentation and other information needed	N/A

DATA SET n. 1– <Case studies specifications, requirements and knowledge gathering> – WP 1– Owner(s): IMT and all partners providing data		
	Repository for deposit of data, metadata, documentation and code	Data will be published in open access in renowned repositories (e.g.Zenodo) and also NINFA open repository
	Access restrictions	No access restrictions for openly available data.
	Data interoperability assessment	N/A
2.3 FAIR DATA – Making data interoperable	Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies	N/A
	Data licensing for wide reuse	The open data will be deposited on public platform such as Zenodo with a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 license.
2.4 FAIR DATA – Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)	Timing of data availability for re-use (incl. indications on embargo)	Data will be made available after the project or before if agreed to by partners.
	Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project)	Third parties who want reuse data are free to do so.
	Restrictions to data re-use	There are no restrictions to data re-use.
	Quality assurance process	Peer review of data.
	Length of time of data re-usability	Published data will be available indefinitely
	Costs estimates for making data FAIR	As data will be stored on institutional drives, the costs are with the institutes. Sharing of data will be done through open and free repositories.
	Data Management Responsibilities	The WP leader (IMT) is responsible for making data openly available

Work Package 2

DATA SET n. 2– <Sensing, Monitoring and Modelling> – WP 2– Owner(s): Wetsus, Sapienza, Aqualia, Deltares, Wings		
1 DATA SUMMARY	Purpose of the Data	The data will describe case studies 1 (CS1) and 2 (CS2). Data from the data sensing network will be added to the existing data from CS2. The main results of the developed hydrological and transport models for CS1 and CS2 will be added as well.

DATA SET n. 2– <Sensing, Monitoring and Modelling> – WP 2– Owner(s): Wetsus, Sapienza, Aqualia, Deltares, Wings		
	Type and Format of data	<p>Existing data describing CS 1 and CS2 will be used. This is mostly data freely available on the internet and data from existing models. Data are related to aquifer properties, surface waters, groundwater, human pressures including withdrawals and potential pollutants, and climatic information. Next to that data from the companies dealing with the groundwater flows will become available. These data will be used as input for models that will make predictions about flows of water and chemicals in groundwater systems.</p> <p>This data will be in the following formats:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - txt, xlsx, Netcdf, Tiff, - Data extracted from existing databases <p>The sensing network will generate the following data at the location of an extraction well for drinking water production</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nitrate concentrations - Conductivity - Temperature - Redox - pH <p>Describe the type of data used or generated within the project, specifying the form and format of the data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Text: field or laboratory notes, survey responses – in plain text, (txt), HTML, XLM, PDF/A ... ▪ Numeric: tables, counts, measurements – in .XLSX, .CSV ... ▪ Audiovisual: images, sound recordings, video – in .JPEG, .JPG, .PNG, .TIFF, AIFF, WAVE, .MP3, .MP4... ▪ For simulated data please state the model, we will used the code MODFLOW with implementations related to transport modeling (MT3D and others), by a commercial software (Groundwater Vistas) and other codes developed from scientific institutions; exportable data will be in TXT, XLS, etc. ▪ Discipline-specific information e.g.: CIF in chemistry ... (specify standard and format) ▪ Instrument specific: equipment output (specify equipment and format)

DATA SET n. 2– <Sensing, Monitoring and Modelling> – WP 2– Owner(s): Wetsus, Sapienza, Aqualia, Deltares, Wings		
	Reused-Data	Most of the data describing CS1 and CS2 are existing data on groundwater flows, concentrations of chemicals. This data is freely available on the internet or provided to the project by companies operating within the case study area (Vitens and Aqualia)
	Data origin	Data can be gathered from different sources, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Observational – data captured in real time- often not reproducible i.e. sensor readings ▪ Experimental – data from lab equipment, often reproducible, but with high costs - i.e. chromatograms, magnetic fields readings... ▪ Simulation – data generated by computational models where model and metadata are more important than output data - i.e. climate models, economic models, materials models,... ▪ Derived/Compiled – data coming from analyses or compilation. Reproducible but with high costs - i.e. the results of text and data mining, compiled databases ▪ Reference or Canonical – collection or conglomeration of smaller (peer-reviewed) datasets published and curated - i.e. chemical structures, gene sequence databanks, spatial data portals
	Data size	The dataset will be growing during the project for 3 reasons: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data describing the case studies is added to the dataset and will grow in time 2. The models will extrapolate and interpolate the data and possibly make predictions in times when no data is/was available 3. For CS2 the sensing network will produce data that will be added to the dataset 4. samples will be collected, and the analysis data will be published

DATA SET n. 2– <Sensing, Monitoring and Modelling> – WP 2– Owner(s): Wetsus, Sapienza, Aqualia, Deltares, Wings		
	Data Security and Storage	Data will be stored on the hard drives of the partners involved. From this data a backup will be available on the institute network drive and backup system. This data is protected Data sharing between partners will be using Teams sharing (Microsoft software). Indicate how and where the data are stored and backed-up (i.e. Office computer, Hard Drive, Tape back-up system, Institute network drive, Institute Central Data storage, private Cloud storage ...), briefly describing the data security policy applied.
	Data value (Long Term)	The data is valuable for the project partners and possible other academic institutes that want to use the data for modelling. Also the companies in charge of the groundwater for both CSs might find some value in the data and outcomes of the modeling.
2. FAIR DATA 2.1 FAIR DATA - Making data findable	Discoverability of data (metadata provision)	Meta data will be provided explaining the format, technical, temporal and spatial characteristics of the data.
	Identifiability of data (refer to standard id mechanisms)	N/A
	Naming conventions used	N/A
	Search keywords approach	N/A
	Clear versioning approach	The new version will have the same name as the previous one but a higher number will be given at the end (e.g., V1, V2,
	Standards or procedures for metadata creation applied	N/A
2.2 FAIR DATA – Making data openly accessible	Data openly available or kept close	Most of the data is already openly available as it is gathered from open sources. The data generated by the modelling will be made openly available and published open access. Exported files from the model results will be in table form and in graphic form.

DATA SET n. 2– <Sensing, Monitoring and Modelling> – WP 2– Owner(s): Wetsus, Sapienza, Aqualia, Deltares, Wings		
	How data will be made available	The data will be published open access on a freely accessible repository (e.g. DANS or 4TU)
	Methods or SW tools for data access	Model output from licensed software will be transformed in formats to be easily imported in free software and code related to numerical modeling (e.g. FREEWAT, produced by previous H2020 EU projects)
	SW documentation and other information needed	The software requirements to access all data will be published together with the data
	Repository for deposit of data, metadata, documentation and code	Data will be published open access in renowned repositories like (Zenodo, 4TU and DANS)
	Access restrictions	In principle there are no restrictions to the availability of the data, only if they are subject to application of IP. If IP is granted, data will be made open access.
	Data interoperability assessment	Assess the level of interoperability of the dataset. Indicate data and metadata vocabularies, standards and methodologies followed to facilitate interoperability. Indicate if open standards are used, and (if you know) the range of utilization of proprietary SW and methodologies used to generate and manage the data.
2.3 FAIR DATA – Making data interoperable	Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies	N/A
	Data licensing for wide reuse	N/A
2.4 FAIR DATA – Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)	Timing of data availability for re-use (incl. indications on embargo)	Data will be made available after the project or sooner when all project partners agree.
	Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project)	Published data will be available open access and therefore also to third parties. Data stored on institutional drives will only be available to institutes and for project partners on request.
	Restrictions to data re-use	Data reuse is taken care of in the grant agreement

DATA SET n. 2– <Sensing, Monitoring and Modelling> – WP 2– Owner(s): Wetsus, Sapienza, Aqualia, Deltares, Wings		
	Quality assurance process	N/A
	Length of time of data re-usability	Published data will be available indefinite
	Costs estimates for making data FAIR	As data will be stored on institutional drives, the costs are with the institutes. Sharing of data will be done through open and free repositories.
	Data Management Responsibilities	The WP leader (Wetsus) is responsible that data is made openly available

Work Package 3

DATA SET n. 3– <Results on laboratory scale optimisation and on-site demonstration for urban runoff, wastewater and agriculture leachates treatment> – WP 3 – Owner(s): LEITAT, IMT, HIDROTEC, AQUALIA		
1 DATA SUMMARY	Purpose of the Data	The data will describe the obtained results at laboratory scale for the treatment of urban runoff, wastewater and agriculture leachates.
	Type and Format of data	<p>Existing knowledge regarding metals, hydrocarbons and microplastics removal from wastewater and urban runoff will be used as basis for the development of the train of technologies.</p> <p>During technology optimisation process, the following data will be generated:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Text: operation protocols, laboratory notes, state of the art – in plain text and/or PDF. ▪ Numeric: laboratory results, water quality analysis data, KPI quantification – in Excel file ▪ Audiovisual: images and video of experimental setup and operation– in .JPEG, .JPG, .PNG, .MP4. <p>Regarding water reuse legislation parameters and KPI evaluation, data will be generated as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Text: regulation key parameters in plain text and/or PDF.

DATA SET n. 3– <Results on laboratory scale optimisation and on-sire demonstration for urban runoff, wastewater and agriculture leachates treatment> – WP 3 – Owner(s): LEITAT, IMT, HIDROTEC, AQUALIA		
	Reused-Data	Data from previous projects (i.e. FERTIMANURE) will be used as baseline for technology optimisation. Public data from the project (and other related projects) will be considered for technologies design. In addition, identified technology bottlenecks will be tackled for improving treatment results.
	Data origin	Data will be generated and registered from the following sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Observational: data captured in real time by equipment sensors, product images, pictures from germination tests and sample analysis data. ▪ Experimental: data regarding samples evolution during the experiment. Different analysis techniques will be used, such as TOC, spectroscopy, digestion, drying... ▪ Derived/Compiled: compiled regulation from different European countries regarding groundwater quality, bio-fertilisers and water reuse policies. ▪ Reference or Canonical: gene sequence databanks for comparing genome sequencing and applied to q-PCR procedures for ARG identification
	Data size	Dataset regarding experimental data will be growing as new data may be added, while not removing old data for having a clear picture of technology optimisation and performance. Data regarding regulation compilation will be revisable as regulation could be modified during the project duration and the dataset should be revised accordingly. The expected size of data generated by experimental data will be 5 MB for each experiment, overall adding up to 1 GB. In addition, text files regarding regulation compilation are expected to need up to 500 MB.
	Data Security and Storage	Data will be stored in Leitát's sharepoint in the shared Teams folder, which can be only accessed through personalised invitation. In addition, some information can be stored in involved researcher's office computer, which can be used as back-up.
	Data value (Long Term)	Data could be useful both for partners and researchers as can be used as state of the art for build on new trains of technologies. Also, it can be re-used for the removal of recovery Describe to whom the data could useful. Estimate potential value of long-term re-use of the data.

DATA SET n. 3– <Results on laboratory scale optimisation and on-sire demonstration for urban runoff, wastewater and agriculture leachates treatment> – WP 3 – Owner(s): LEITAT, IMT, HIDROTEC, AQUALIA		
2. FAIR DATA 2.1 FAIR DATA - Making data findable	Discoverability of data (metadata provision)	Metadata will be available at a public repository. In addition, for scientific publications, experimental raw data will be available on request.
	Identifiability of data (refer to standard id mechanisms)	Scientific publications will be identified by a DOI identifier.
	Naming conventions used	Electronic files and folders will be identified by coding NINFA – WP3 – T3.X – [Main content]
	Search keywords approach	Proper keywords will be provided for each publication depending on the scope. However, common keywords such as GROUNDWATER, and QUALITY will be used.
	Clear versioning approach	In public file storage system, each version will be tagged at the end of the file name with vx.
2.2 FAIR DATA – Making data openly accessible	Data openly available or kept close	Data regarding experimental set up and performance can be made accessible under demand, according to journal policies. Data regarding DC water quality and specific information are restricted to consortium partners.
	How data will be made available	Data will be stored in a repository, which can be accessed upon personal request.
	SW documentation and other information needed	If necessary, a readme file will be added for abbreviations or additional information for understanding the data
	Repository for deposit of data, metadata, documentation and code	Data and metadata will be available in open repositories (or private repositories with open access under request). Repositories can be institutional (hosted by each partner). Data manager will assess the possibility to set a certified open repository for all data generated within the project.
	Access restrictions	Green open access publications will be available 18 - 24 months after the subscriber publication according to journal embargo periods.
	Data interoperability assessment	Readme files will be provided for each dataset if customised coding or abbreviations are used.

DATA SET n. 3– <Results on laboratory scale optimisation and on-sire demonstration for urban runoff, wastewater and agriculture leachates treatment> – WP 3 – Owner(s): LEITAT, IMT, HIDROTEC, AQUALIA		
2.3 FAIR DATA – Making data interoperable	Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies	N/A
	Data licensing for wide reuse	Data and results will be published under Creative Commons 4 licenses.
2.4 FAIR DATA – Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)	Timing of data availability for re-use (incl. indications on embargo)	Published data will be available for its reuse after 18 – 24 months of embargo period if it is published in Green Open Access. Gold Open Access publications will be available for re-use since its publication.
	Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project)	On request available data will be open for third parties while restricted data regarding DC sensitive information will remain restrictive and property of each DC owner
	Restrictions to data re-use	Specific information regarding customised train of technologies for tackling additional needs can be potentially available for exploitation purposes after the signature of confidentiality agreements.
	Quality assurance process	Experimental data quality will be assured through the performance of duplicates (or triplicates) if applicable. Journal publications quality will be assured through a peer-reviewed process.
	Length of time of data re-usability	Time constrain of data re-usability is related to the advances on the technique not the data itself. Data can be re-used until the future SOTA goes beyond what has been achieved.
	Costs estimates for making data FAIR	Open Access publications of the data produced have a dedicated part of the budget. In the case of budget shortage, Green Open Access publication can be considered.
	Data Management Responsibilities	Within the project, LEITAT as coordinator will be managing a backup repository for all generated dataset. In addition, each participating partner will be responsible of managing the generated data (experimental and documental) under FAIR principles.

Work Package 4

DATA SET 4– < Risk and sustainability assessment> – WP 4– Owner (s): Deltares		
1 DATA SUMMARY	Purpose of the Data	To be used for AI modelling, risk assessment.
	Type and Format of data	<p>Generated in other WP's and casestudies</p> <p>Describe the type of data used or generated within the project, specifying the form and format of the data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Text: field or laboratory notes, survey responses – in plain text, (txt), HTML, XLM, PDF/A ... ▪ Numeric: tables, counts, measurements – in .XLSX, .CSV ... ▪ Audiovisual: images, sound recordings, video – in .JPEG, .JPG, .PNG, .TIFF, AIFF, WAVE, .MP3, .MP4... ▪ For simulated data please state the model, model type and computer code... - and specify data type and format) ▪ Discipline-specific information e.g.: CIF in chemistry ... (specify standard and format) ▪ Instrument specific: equipment output (specify equipment and format)
	Reused-Data	<p>Generated in other WP's and case studies.</p> <p>Indicate if you re-use existing data (generated outside the project). If so, explain how.</p>

DATA SET 4– < Risk and sustainability assessment> – WP 4– Owner (s): Deltares		
	Data origin	<p>Data origin: see other WP's.</p> <p>Define <u>and describe</u> the origin/source of your data. Data can be gathered from different sources, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Observational – data captured in real time- often not reproducible i.e. sensor readings, images, telemetries, sample data... ▪ Experimental – data from lab equipment, often reproducible, but with high costs - i.e. chromatograms, magnetic fields readings... ▪ Simulation – data generated by computational models where model and metadata are more important than output data - i.e. climate models, economic models, materials models,... ▪ Derived/Compiled – data coming from analyses or compilation. Reproducible but with high costs - i.e. the results of text and data mining, compiled databases <p>Reference or Canonical – collection or conglomeration of smaller (peer-reviewed) datasets published and curated - i.e. chemical structures, gene sequence databanks, spatial data portals</p>
	Data size	N/A
	Data Security and Storage	N/A
	Data value (Long Term)	N/A
2. FAIR DATA 2.1 FAIR DATA - Making data findable	Discoverability of data (metadata provision)	N/A
	Identifiability of data (refer to standard id mechanisms)	N/A
	Naming conventions used	N/A
	Search keywords approach	N/A
	Clear versioning approach	N/A

DATA SET 4– < Risk and sustainability assessment> – WP 4– Owner (s): Deltares		
	Standards or procedures for metadata creation applied	N/A
2.2 FAIR DATA – Making data openly accessible	Data openly available or kept close	After data processing, the results are shared on teams with the consortium.
	How data will be made available	N/A
	Methods or SW tools for data access	N/A
	SW documentation and other information needed	N/A
	Repository for deposit of data, metadata, documentation and code	N/A
	Access restrictions	N/A
	Data interoperability assessment	Assess the level of interoperability of the dataset. Indicate data and metadata vocabularies, standards and methodologies followed to facilitate interoperability. Indicate if open standards are used, and (if you know) the range of utilization of proprietary SW and methodologies used to generate and manage the data.
2.3 FAIR DATA – Making data interoperable	Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies	N/A
	Data licensing for wide reuse	N/A
2.4 FAIR DATA – Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)	Timing of data availability for re-use (incl. indications on embargo)	N/A

DATA SET 4– < Risk and sustainability assessment> – WP 4– Owner (s): Deltares		
	Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project)	N/A
	Restrictions to data re-use	N/A
	Quality assurance process	N/A
	Length of time of data re-usability	N/A
	Costs estimates for making data FAIR	N/A
	Data Management Responsibilities	N/A

Work Package 5

DATA SET n. 5– <Correlation Table> – WP 5 – Owner(s): WINGS		
1 DATA SUMMARY	Purpose of the Data	Purpose of the data set is to extract statistical conclusions regarding chemical/physical components found in groundwaters as well as correlations between water quality and weather changes.
	Type and Format of data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The type of data used are in the form of a .XLSX file.
	Reused-Data	The data are a subset of groundwater and meteorological data for CS1 of the NINFA project.
	Data origin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The chemical/physical data are Experimental, gathered from different samplings through chemical analysis.
	Data size	<i>The size of the input data is fixed around 3MB.</i>
	Data Security and Storage	The data are stored in a Hard Drive. In the future a backup file will be created in a private Cloud Storage.
	Data value (Long Term)	The data could be valuable to applications where chemical/physical water quality correlations are needed. Furthermore the effect of different weather scenarios on chemical components and their values could be investigated further.

DATA SET n. 5– <Correlation Table> – WP 5 – Owner(s): WINGS		
2. FAIR DATA 2.1 FAIR DATA - Making data findable	Discoverability of data (metadata provision)	N/A
	Identifiability of data (refer to standard id mechanisms)	N/A
	Naming conventions used	Since the output is a single .xlsx file the naming is simple and self-explainable. No specific system/technique has been used.
	Search keywords approach	Weather data, chemical components, correlations, water quality, potability.
	Clear versioning approach	No versioning needed.
	Standards or procedures for metadata creation applied	N/A
2.2 FAIR DATA – Making data openly accessible	Data openly available or kept close	The input data has been shared by the CS1 stakeholders. The output data has been provided to the partners by uploading it to the Teams folder.
	How data will be made available	The data will not be available for public use.
	Methods or SW tools for data access	A simple .XLSX file. Office software.
	SW documentation and other information needed	Abbreviations used mostly in the weather measurement variables.
	Repository for deposit of data, metadata, documentation and code	N/A
	Access restrictions	<i>No limitations occur to any of the partners.</i>
	Data interoperability assessment	N/A

DATA SET n. 5– <Correlation Table> – WP 5 – Owner(s): WINGS		
2.3 FAIR DATA – Making data interoperable	Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies	N/A
	Data licensing for wide reuse	N/A
2.4 FAIR DATA – Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)	Timing of data availability for re-use (incl. indications on embargo)	N/A
	Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project)	N/A
	Restrictions to data re-use	Confidentiality agreement of the NINFA project.
	Quality assurance process	Data has been gathered from multiple sources or validated peers and reviewed by partners to assure quality.
	Length of time of data re-usability	N/A
	Costs estimates for making data FAIR	Low FAIR costs.
	Data Management Responsibilities	N/A

Work Package 6

DATA SET n. 6– <Dissemination and Communication> – WP 6 – Owner(s): CETRI		
1 DATA SUMMARY	Purpose of the Data	Reporting for Dissemination and Communication. Also repository of publications and feedback from stakeholders..
	Type and Format of data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Text: survey responses – in plain text, (txt), .pdf , ▪ Numeric: tables, counts,from google analytics – in .XLSX ▪ Audiovisual: images, sound recordings, video – in .JPEG, .JPG, .PNG, ., .MP3, .MP4...
	Reused-Data	N/A
	Data origin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Derived/Compiled – data coming from workshops, events, conferences, surveys, website, newsletter, social media channels
	Data size	<p>The dataset is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Growing: new data may be added, but the old data is never changed or deleted <p>The data size may reach up to 1 GB</p>
	Data Security and Storage	Personal Computer secured by personal password and no one else has access.
	Data value (Long Term)	To researchers , the industry, stakeholders
2. FAIR DATA 2.1 FAIR DATA - Making data findable	Discoverability of data (metadata provision)	The data is documented based on the type and date of the event it was collected.
	Identifiability of data (refer to standard id mechanisms)	The data will be in open access and will be identified by date and event collected by. ...)
	Naming conventions used	Haven't set a naming system yet, but the date the data will be collected will be included in the naming. .
	Search keywords approach	N/A
	Clear versioning approach	N/A

DATA SET n. 6– <Dissemination and Communication> – WP 6 – Owner(s): CETRI		
	Standards or procedures for metadata creation applied	N/A
2.2 FAIR DATA – Making data openly accessible	Data openly available or kept close	Data collected for dissemination and communication purposes will be openly available, also data collected from google analytics will be openly available.
	How data will be made available	through deposit in the project’s open repository.
	Methods or SW tools for data access	N/A
	SW documentation and other information needed	N/A
	Repository for deposit of data, metadata, documentation and code	In the NNFA repository during the duration of the project. After that, hasn’t been decided yet.
	Access restrictions	No restrictions
	Data interoperability assessment	N/A
2.3 FAIR DATA – Making data interoperable	Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies	N/A
	Data licensing for wide reuse	N/A
2.4 FAIR DATA – Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)	Timing of data availability for re-use (incl. indications on embargo)	N/A
	Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project)	N/A
	Restrictions to data re-use	N/A

DATA SET n. 6– <Dissemination and Communication> – WP 6 – Owner(s): CETRI		
	Quality assurance process	standardized data recording,
	Length of time of data re-usability	N/A
	Costs estimates for making data FAIR	N/A
	Data Management Responsibilities	N/A

Conclusion

To conclude, this living document will help guide the data management of the NINFA project. It will be regularly updated as the project evolves, and the overall strategy of the consortium develops. This deliverable will act as an initial copy and has been drafted with a research data management policy that is aligned with the EC Horizon 2020 data management policy requirements.

Appendix 1: Blank template for dataset management

DATA SET n. X– <name> – WP X – Owner(s): XXX		
1 DATA SUMMARY	Purpose of the Data	State the purpose of the data collection/generation, indicating the relation with the objectives of the project.
	Type and Format of data	<p>...</p> <p>Describe the type of data used or generated within the project, specifying the form and format of the data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Text: field or laboratory notes, survey responses – in plain text, (txt), HTML, XLM, PDF/A ... ▪ Numeric: tables, counts, measurements – in .XLSX, .CSV ... ▪ Audiovisual: images, sound recordings, video – in .JPEG, .JPG, .PNG, .TIFF, AIFF, WAVE, .MP3, .MP4... ▪ For simulated data please state the model, model type and computer code... - and specify data type and format) ▪ Discipline-specific information e.g.: CIF in chemistry ... (specify standard and format) ▪ Instrument specific: equipment output (specify equipment and format)
	Reused-Data	<p>...</p> <p>Indicate if you re-use existing data (generated outside the project). If so, explain how.</p>

DATA SET n. X- <name> – WP X – Owner(s): XXX		
	Data origin	<p>...</p> <p>Define <u>and describe</u> the origin/source of your data. Data can be gathered from different sources, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Observational – data captured in real time- often not reproducible i.e. sensor readings, images, telemetries, sample data... ▪ Experimental – data from lab equipment, often reproducible, but with high costs - i.e. chromatograms, magnetic fields readings... ▪ Simulation – data generated by computational models where model and metadata are more important than output data - i.e. climate models, economic models, materials models,... ▪ Derived/Compiled – data coming from analyses or compilation. Reproducible but with high costs - i.e. the results of text and data mining, compiled databases ▪ Reference or Canonical – collection or conglomeration of smaller (peer-reviewed) datasets published and curated - i.e. chemical structures, gene sequence databanks, spatial data portals
	Data size	<p>...</p> <p>Indicate if the dataset is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fixed: never change after being collected or generated ▪ Growing: new data may be added, but the old data is never changed or deleted ▪ Revisable: new data may be added, and old data may be changed or deleted <p>Then, indicate the quantity / expected size of data generated (by experiment and overall) – for example: <i>50MB for each experiment, overall adding up to 5GB</i></p> <p>In case not just digital archiving is required, indicated quantities of other form of storage – for example: <i>2 drawers of a standard filing cabinet</i></p>
	Data Security and Storage	<p>...</p> <p>Indicate how and where the data are stored and backed-up (i.e. Office computer, Hard Drive, Tape back-up system, Institute network drive, Institute Central Data storage, private Cloud storage ...), briefly describing the data security policy applied.</p>

DATA SET n. X- <name> – WP X – Owner(s): XXX		
	Data value (Long Term)	... Describe to whom the data could useful. Estimate potential value of long-term re-use of the data.
2. FAIR DATA 2.1 FAIR DATA - Making data findable	Discoverability of data (metadata provision)	... Explain how data are documented and if metadata are provided, listing the information made available/discoverable. In case of materials model simulations attach a dataset specific MODA.
	Identifiability of data (refer to standard id mechanisms)	... Indicate how data are made identifiable, if a standard permanent identifier assignation scheme is used (i.e. ARK, DOI, PURL, URN, MODA ...)
	Naming conventions used	... Describe the system used to name and structure electronic files and folders. Refer also to any file renaming procedure or tools used.
	Search keywords approach	... Indicate the approach to keywords generation, indexing and tagging. (For materials modelling the MODA provide this answer)
	Clear versioning approach	... Describe the versioning and traceability approach used (especially if the dataset is growing or revisable).
	Standards or procedures for metadata creation applied	... Indicate and describe the procedures and templates applied for the creation of metadata. Refer to any institute policy or recommendations by specific initiatives that are applied. In case the procedure to create metadata is not (only) manual, but automatic, refer also to any tools used for metadata creation. Some references: MODA, EMMO (European Materials Modelling Ontology), Dublin Core Metadata Initiative, DataCite Metadata Schema, Open Archives Initiative Object Reuse and Exchange, ISAtools ... If there are no standards in your discipline, describe what type of metadata will be created and how.

DATA SET n. X- <name> – WP X – Owner(s): XXX		
2.2 FAIR DATA – Making data openly accessible	Data openly available or kept close	... Indicate ownership of the data, if it is openly available or can be made openly available. Indicate if data access is restricted, to what users, and explain the reasons.
	How data will be made available	... Indicate how you intend to make data available – i.e. through deposit in an open repository or through a platform for a specific users group or upon personal request.
	Methods or SW tools for data access	... Indicate methods and SW tools needed to access the data. Clarify if the relevant software (e.g. in open source code) is included in the data set.
	SW documentation and other information needed	... Indicate also any specific SW documentation that is needed to access the data. Indicate also any additional information that is needed to understand the data (i.e. abbreviations, supplementary notes).
	Repository for deposit of data, metadata, documentation and code	... Indicate the (open or private) repositories in which the data, metadata, documentation and code are stored and/or those in which they will be stored in the future. They might be disciplinary or institutional, open or restricted - eg. Zenodo, 4TU.Centre for Research Data, Nanomaterial Registry, Hazardous Substance Databanks... Preference should be given to certified repositories, which support open access, where possible.
	Access restrictions	... Indicate if there are limitations and restrictions to access the data, and if they are linked to a specific timeframe. Explain how access will be provided after these restrictions are lifted.
	Data interoperability assessment	Assess the level of interoperability of the dataset. Indicate data and metadata vocabularies, standards and methodologies followed to facilitate interoperability. Indicate if open standards are used, and (if you know) the range of utilization of proprietary SW and methodologies used to generate and manage the data.
2.3 FAIR DATA – Making data interoperable	Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies	... Refer to commonly used ontologies to map the dataset, considering also the use of existing common platforms and tools – eg: EMMO, BFO, MatONTO, Materials Ontology ...

DATA SET n. X- <name> – WP X – Owner(s): XXX		
	Data licensing for wide reuse	... If applicable, define data licensing approach for the dataset wide reuse. Indicate the chosen licenses tools (eg. Creative Commons, Open Data Commons, Apache License 2.0, BSD ...).
2.4 FAIR DATA – Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)	Timing of data availability for re-use (incl. indications on embargo)	... If applicable, define the timeframe for making data available for re-use. Indicate any embargo period if required.
	Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project)	... Indicate any limitation to the use of the data by Third Parties, after the end of the project.
	Restrictions to data re-use	... Indicate and explain any restriction to the re-use of data (i.e. confidentiality agreements, other issues).
	Quality assurance process	... Explain how quality of the data is assured, how the consistency and quality of data collection is controlled and documented (i.e. calibration, repeat samples and measurements, standardized data capture, standardized data recording, data entry validation, peer review of data, representation with controlled vocabularies...).
	Length of time of data re-usability	... Indicate the time limit for the data re-usability, if any.
	Costs estimates for making data FAIR	... Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR (<i>findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable</i>) and describe how you intend or might be able to cover these costs (i.e. institute dedicated resources, dedicated part of the project budget ...).
	Data Management Responsibilities Identify responsibilities for data management of this dataset (within your research group and institute, and within the project if applicable)

